

Polyamino Chelates of Cu(II), Ni(II), Pd(II) and Pt(II) Diphenates

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The complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Pd(II) and Pt(II) diphenates with dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline have been prepared and characterised on the basis of chemical analysis, conductance and magnetic measurements, I.R. and electronic spectral studies. All the complexes were found to have a square planar structure.

1:1 CHELATES of bivalent transition metal ions with dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline form hydroxo complexes^{1,2} which can further react with another acidic ligand and hence the present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of such type of complexes using diphenic acid as an acidic ligand.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: All the reagents, used were of A. R. (BDH) quality. The solutions of metal salts in distilled water and of diphenic acid, dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline in methanol were prepared.

Apparatus: As reported earlier³. Electronic spectra were obtained with CZ-SPECORD-uv. vis recording spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the complexes:

The reactants were mixed in the ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 and the mixture was refluxed for half an hour at $\approx 70^\circ$ in the case of Ni(II) complexes (complex no. 1 and 2) but was kept overnight in the case of

others (complex no. 3 to 8). The precipitates were obtained on cooling the mixture at room temperature while the pink crystals of Ni(II) complexes were obtained on cooling the mixture in the ice bath for twenty four hours. These were filtered, washed with distilled water, Cu(II), Pd(II) and Pt(II) complexes were washed finally with methanol also and the precipitates were then dried in the oven at $\approx 80^\circ$. The results of chemical analysis and the spectral data are given in Table-1.

The values of molar conductance (≈ 10 mhos) of palladium(II) complexes in DMF and of copper(II) and platinum(II) complexes in acetone indicated their nonelectrolytic nature.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes showed the diamagnetic behaviour of Ni(II) and Pd(II) complexes and a paramagnetic character with a value 1.81 B.M. of Cu(II) complexes. The electronic spectra of Pd(II) complexes in DMF, Pt(II) and Cu(II) complexes in methanol and of Ni(II) complexes in acetone indicated their square planar structure. The orbital energy differences Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 for $F_2 = 10F_4 = 700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

TABLE-1 ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complexes	% Calc (Found)			$\nu_{\max} \text{ Cm}^{-1}$					
		C	H	M	1		2		3	
1.	[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂) (C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄)]	63.33(62.79)	3.51(3.34)	12.90(12.31)	41100	33500	32200	30500	22500	
2.	[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂) (C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄)]	65.17(64.88)	3.34(3.19)	12.26(11.67)	37000	34500	31500	30000	23000	
3.	[Pd(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂) (C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄)]	57.32(57.00)	3.18(3.00)	21.17(20.39)	35000	32500	30000	27800	22500	
4.	[Pd(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂) (C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄)]	59.27(58.88)	3.03(2.89)	20.21(20.00)	35000	32500	39000	27800	22500	
5.	[Pt(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂) (C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄)]	48.72(48.39)	2.70(2.55)	33.00(33.85)	41000	39150	25500			
6.	[Pt(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂) (C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄)]	50.72(50.48)	2.60(2.55)	31.71(32.49)	40000	39000	35000			
7.	[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂) (C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄)]	62.67(62.25)	3.48(3.16)	13.81(13.55)	21500	19500	15500			
8.	[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂) (C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄)]	64.52(64.38)	3.30(3.18)	13.13(13.00)	21500	19000	15000			
	Orbital energy differences (cm ⁻¹)	Complex no.								
		1	2	3	4	5	6			
	Δ_1	24950	24950	24950	24950	—	—			
	Δ_2	9400	9400	6700	6700	12500	12500			
	Δ_3	4650	2350	1850	850	-3600	-2700			

were calculated for Ni(II), Pd(II) and Pt(II) complexes. The separation Δ_1 for these complexes was the largest of the three orbital parameters which indicated that the $d_x^2 - y^2$ was much more strongly antibonding than any of the other d orbitals. The separation Δ_2 decreased regularly in going from Ni(II) to Pt(II) complexes which indicated that the d_x^2 was more unstable than d_{xz} , d_{yz} in the complexes of Ni(II) and Pd(II) and d_x^2 was more stable than d_{xz} , d_{yz} in the complex of Pt(II). This was compatible with the idea that the axial interaction of the solvent molecules decreased in going from Ni(II) to Pt(II).

The bands obtained at 740 cm^{-1} in the i.r. spectra of ligands were shifted to 760 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of Ni(II) complexes and 770 , 780 and 800 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Cu(II), Pd(II) and Pt(II) complexes respectively. The second band obtained at 830 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of free ligand was shifted to 850 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Ni(II) complexes while this band was observed at 870 cm^{-1} in the case of other metal complexes. All these bands gained intensity in the spectra of complexes which was also a characteristic feature of dipyrindyl and phenanthroline complexes^{4,5}. The strong bands

obtained at 1700 cm^{-1} and 1450 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-O} in the spectrum of free diphenic acid were shifted to 1600 cm^{-1} and 1380 cm^{-1} respectively in the spectra of Ni(II) complexes and to 1600 cm^{-1} and 1440 cm^{-1} in the spectra of other metal complexes. The stretching frequency due to M-O was obtained at about 500 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the complexes.

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